

TRIDENT

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Data Management Plan

An overview of the development approach

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The DMP

- A key element of good data management
- A blueprint for what will be done with the data during and projects end
- A living document

Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020, European Commission, 2016

Developing the first version

- A top-down approach
- Mapping good practices and aligned them with the structural components of the DMP
- To evolve from core practices to more specific ones, accounting data stakeholders requirements

DMP components

- Data summary
- FAIR data
 - Repository for data availability
 - Data documentation and metadata
 - File naming convention
- Data security
- Ethics and Legal Compliance

Data Inventory Register

- A catalog of the data collected or produced by the project
- Detailed metadata regarding the datasets
- Will be available for all partners
- Incrementally updated at each DMP version

J	K	L	M	N
Source	Format	Size	Dataset Duration	Data Collection Instrument
Where the data originates. Is the data reused? Recommended best practice is to identify the related resource.	The file format. Example : <i>txt/xml/csv</i>	The total weight of the dataset (when applicable) Example: <i>4gb.</i>	[When applicable] The extant or time taken to play or execute the dataset. For instance the duration of a video file.	The instruments used to generate and or process the data.

Metadata

- Responsible Party
- Number of data files
- Source
- Size
- Format
- Support Documentation
- Storage Location
- Repository URL
- DOI
- Other

Main Principles

- *As Open as Possible, as Closed as necessary*
- Persistent identifiers are assigned and included in the metadata
- Metadata should be accesible even when data may not be publicly available
- Metadata is based on standard vocabularies

INESC TEC institutional data repository

- Open source RDM system
- Accessed by any user at any time
- Deposit is the responsibility of the DMP manager
- Provision of DOI and citation information
- Standardized and customizable
- Data backups performed daily, while tap backup is performed weekly

The screenshot shows the INESC TEC Research Data Repository website. The header includes the INESC TEC logo, navigation links for Datasets, Organizations, Groups, and About, and a search bar. A welcome message states: "Welcome to the INESC TEC research data repository. This data repository showcases datasets produced or used by INESC TEC researchers and their partners. It is an embodiment of our institutional commitment to Open Data in research." Below this is a featured section for INESC TEC Research Data Repository. A search bar on the right contains the text "E.g. environment" and has a search icon. Below the search bar are popular tags: "load", "electricity distrib...", and "flexibility". The main content area features two dataset cards. The first card is for "CS: Computer Science" with the mission statement "The Computer Science Cluster mission is to..." and a description: "Describing data in image format: Proposal of a metadata model and controlled ... Research data management (RDM) includes people with different needs, specific scientific contexts, and diverse...". The second card is for "INESC TEC" with the mission statement "The Institute for Systems and Computer..." and a description: "Describing data in image format: Proposal of a metadata model and controlled ... Research data management (RDM) includes people with different needs, specific scientific contexts, and diverse...". Below this is another card for "PhysioIntent: Multimodal dataset for human intention prediction research" with the description: "PhysioIntent database was acquired during the master thesis at INESC TEC. The master thesis will be published in..."

INESC TEC institutional data repository

Classification of online health messages

Classification of online health messages

The dataset has 487 annotated messages taken from Medhelp, an online health forum with several health communities (<https://www.medhelp.org/>). It was built in a master thesis entitled "Automatic categorization of health-related messages in online health communities" of the Master in Informatics and Computing Engineering of the Faculty of Engineering of the University of Porto. It expands a dataset created in a previous work [see Relation metadata] whose objective was to propose a classification scheme to analyze messages exchanged in online health forums.

A website was built to allow the classification of additional messages collected from Medhelp. After using a Python script to scrape the five most recent discussions from popular forums (<https://www.medhelp.org/forums/list>), we sampled 285 messages from them to annotate. Each message was classified three times by anonymous people in 11 categories from April 2022 until the end of May 2022. For each message, the rater picked the categories associated with the message and its emotional polarity (positive, neutral, and negative).

Our dataset is organized in two CSV files, one containing information regarding the 885 (=3*285) classifications collected via crowdsourcing (CrowdsourcingClassification.csv) and the other containing the 487 messages with their final and consensual classifications (FinalClassification.csv).

The readMe file provides detailed information about the two .csv files.

Data and Resources

-
readMe
↗ Explore ▾
-
Crowdsourcing Classification
Information regarding the 885 (=3*285) classifications collected via...
↗ Explore ▾
-
Final Classification
487 messages with their final and consensual classifications.
↗ Explore ▾

Additional Info

Field	Value
Source	Medhelp
Author	João Abelha
State	active
Last Updated	July 6, 2022, 2:03 PM (UTC+01:00)
Created	July 6, 2022, 1:55 PM (UTC+01:00)
Citation	Abelha, J. (2022). Classification of online health messages [Data set]. INESC TEC. https://doi.org/10.25747/DG9G-A217
DOI	https://doi.org/10.25747/DG9G-A217
dc.Coverage.Temporal	April - May 2022
dc.File.Size	476 kb
dc.Format	.csv
dc.Relation	Carla Teixeira Lopes and Bárbara Guimarães Da Silva. "A classification scheme for analyses of messages exchanged in online health forums." Proceedings of the The Information Behaviour Conference (ISIC 2018). 2018.

DOI is registered by the DMP manager, by filling out minimal citation information in the DataCite service

Catch-all repository

Communities created and curated by Zenodo users

Showing 0 to 10 out of 11322 communities.

Sort by ▾

Transform to Open Science Featured

Transform to Open Science (TOPS) is a \$40 million, 5-year mission, led by NASA's Science Mission Directorate's Open-Source Science initiative. Within the TOPS mission, NASA is designating 2023 as the Year Of Open Science, a community initiative to spark change and inspire open science engagement through events and activities that will accelerate adoption of open science practices. TOPS is only the starting point, the science community needs agencies and organizations to make a long-term commitment to support building an inclusive open science community over the next decade. TOPS website: <https://science.nasa.gov/open-science/transform-to-open-science>

Biodiversity Literature Repository View

A community to share publications related to bio-systematics. The goal is to provide open access to publications cited in publications or in combination with scientific names open access FAIR data with focus on taxon treatments and figures liberated...

Curated by: coviho-admin

European Commission Funded Research (OpenAIRE) View

Curated by: ZENODO

My communities New

INESC TEC
Identifier: inesc tec

Actions ▾

📁 New upload

Community

INESC TEC

INESC TEC is a private non-profit research association, with Public Interest status, dedicated to scientific research and technological development, technology transfer, advanced consulting and training, and pre-incubation of new technology-based companies.

This community showcases research outputs produced by INESC TEC researchers.

Data policies by journals or editors

PLOS ONE

Acceptable Data Sharing Methods

Deposition within data repository (strongly recommended)

All data and related metadata underlying reported findings should be deposited in appropriate public data repositories, unless already provided as part of a submitted article. Repositories may be either subject-specific repositories that accept specific types of structured data, or cross-disciplinary generalist repositories that accept multiple data types.

If field-specific standards for data deposition exist, PLOS requires authors to comply with these standards. Authors should select repositories appropriate to their field of study (for example, ArrayExpress or GEO for microarray data; GenBank, EMBL, or DDBJ for gene sequences).

The Data Availability Statement must list the name of the repository or repositories as well as digital object identifiers (DOIs), accession numbers or codes, or other [persistent identifiers](#) for all relevant data.

Data Availability: Relevant data and supplementary material to this paper are available in the Zenodo repository: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1039241>. The material includes the sequence videos of single and double stainings and the 3D models of single and double stainings. S4 Video shows quality control using virtual reality. Two supplemental figures and the settings for colour deconvolution are also included in the repository.

Data policies by journals or editors

Wiley's Data Sharing Policies

	Data availability statement is published ¹	Data has been shared ²	Data has been peer reviewed ³	Example Wiley journals
Encourages Data Sharing	Optional	Optional	Optional	
Expects Data Sharing	Required	Optional	Optional	British Journal of Social Psychology
Mandates Data Sharing	Required	Required	Optional	Ecology and Evolution
Mandates Data Sharing and Peer Reviews Data	Required	Required	Required	Geoscience Data Journal American Journal of Political Science

Data Documentation

LEVEL	INFORMATION ELEMENTS
Dataset	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical report for the user to understand how the data were collected and processed. • Citation information to indicate how secondary users will have to cite the data. • Study design, methodology, instruments and measures used.
File or database	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How the files that make up the dataset (or tables in the database) relate to each other. • The format of the files.
Variable and item level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How the object of analysis was produced. • Label explaining the meaning of variables.

Data Documentation

Data and Resources

dock_pose

Files (.txt) containing GPS information regarding the dock.

[Explore](#)

zarco_pose

Files (.txt) containing GPS + IMU information regarding the ASV.

[Explore](#)

readme

General information about dataset.

[Explore](#)

images_left_1

Files (.png) containing the images from the left camera. Part 1

[Explore](#)

The DORA@CRAS dataset was acquired in 3D simulator Gazebo. Different types of docking-based structures were placed in a simulated maritime environment along with other types of objects such as floating buoys and boats. A model of an Autonomous Surface Vehicle (ASV), with a set of incorporated sensors (LiDAR, left and right cameras, GPS, IMU) was sequentially positioned in full circles of increasing distance around the dock. To further increase variety in the dataset, the orientation of the vehicle also varied, by modifying the Euler angles roll, pitch and yaw. This collection process resulted in a dataset of circa 34000 instances, 19000 of which contained a docking platform and 15000 did not.

This dataset includes:

- a folder denominated "pcloud" containing the captured point clouds (.pcd files) with filename as follows:

 - pcloud_xxxxx_y.pcd

- a folder denominated "images" containing the captured images from the left and right cameras (.png files) with filename as follows:

 - image_left_xxxxx_y.png

 - image_right_xxxxx_y.png

- a folder denominated "dock_pose" containing text files with information about position and orientation of the dock, with filename as follows:

 - dock_pose_xxxxx.txt

- a folder denominated "zarco_pose" containing text files with information about position and orientation of the ASV, with filename as follows:

 - zarco_pose_xxxxx.txt

where xxxxx represents the instance number and y the associated label.

File Naming Convention

File names are an essential identifier throughout the data life-cycle

- File names have to remain meaningful and useful beyond the original creator and storage location
- File names should provide metadata about the data file

Make the data easy to access and understand

Elements to consider:

- Description of the content
- Name of creator or team
- Temporal information

survey03.docx VS I_P03_R02_2022-05-01

File Naming Convention

Some conditions must be guaranteed

- Context information
- Consistency
- Avoid special characters and spaces

When adopting a file name convention strategy, a simple quick access guide has to be provided

I_P03_R02_2022-05-01

I = interview (**What?**)

P [n] = participant ID (**Which?**)

R [r] = researcher ID (**Who?**)

Date of interview = YYYY-MM-DD (**When?**)

**Date format follows
ISO 8601 convention**

Demonstration

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